

The realisation of Di Scipio's Audible Ecosystemics n.2: strengths and challenges in the interpretation and notation of machine-independent computer music

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Abstract

This work presents a practical investigation of *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* (Feedback Study) by Agostino Di Scipio (2003), reimplemented within the open-source programming environment Faust (Functional Audio Stream). The work—originally realised in the proprietary Symbolic Sound's Kyma system—explores self-regulating feedback processes between computer, performer, and acoustic space. Feedback tones generated through the interaction of microphones, loudspeakers, and the room's acoustics are analysed and transformed in real time, giving rise to an adaptive sonic behaviour that reflects the structural coupling between system and environment.

This work addresses both the conceptual and technical challenges encountered when translating the score and the original Kyma patch into an open-source, transparent DSP framework. It highlights how small differences in the interpretation of Kyma objects can significantly alter the emergent dynamics of the system, potentially compromising the integrity of the compositional idea if not carefully considered.

Beyond the technical reconstruction, this project situates *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* within a broader reflection on the sustainability and transmission of machine-independent live electronic music. Particular attention goes to consistent implementation of complex musical algorithms via rigorous testing routines, so as to guarantee a suitable technical baseline, which is mandatory for non-trivial, recursive systems.

1. Introduction to *Audible Ecosystemics*

Agostino Di Scipio's *Audible Ecosystemics (AE)* is a cycle of three works (now four) designed both as solo *live electronics* performances and as sound installations. In these works, electroacoustic feedback becomes the source of a concrete notion of interaction: a network of interdependencies among system components, through which dynamic behaviour emerges as the autonomous system (for example, a DSP unit) couples with the surrounding environment. These processes are configured as self-controlled audio feedback loops with a variety of autonomous sound transformations, unfolding in the performance space as a process of self-

organisation, following bio-cybernetic principles such as system/ambience coupling, nonlinear dynamics, and emergent adaptation within a complex feedback network (Di Scipio 2003, Sanfilippo and Valle 2013, Sanfilippo 2023).

Drawing a clear lineage from Alvin Lucier’s *I Am Sitting in a Room* (1969)—in which recursive feedback exposes the resonant frequencies and performative agency of the space itself—Di Scipio extends this principle into *live algorithmic interventions* where the system’s behaviour is co-determined by environmental conditions and performer actions. Each piece in the cycle can thus be understood as a distinct sonic ecology, organised around a specific class of elementary sonic materials: impulses (*AE no.1*), sinusoids (*AE no.2*), or background noise (*AE no.3*).

1.1. Audible Ecosystemics n.2

Prepared for the world premiere on 18 October 2003 at the concert “*Past, Present and Future of Music and Technology*” at IPEM in Ghent, and developed through an extensive period of site-specific experimentation in the Church of Santa Caterina in L’Aquila (Italy), *Audible Ecosystemics n.2 (Feedback Study)* is based on Larsen tones generated through direct feedback coupling between distributed microphones and loudspeakers in the performance space. In this work, sounds arise from the selective reinforcement of the space’s resonant modes, producing and processing tones as an emergent by-product of the physical and computational resources.

The work marks a decisive step towards fully self-organising feedback systems. A crucial technical and conceptual turning point concerned finding strategies and mechanisms for energetic regulation and variation: finding how to maintain inherently unstable electroacoustic phenomena in a stable, conditional state that could be further elaborated. In this sense, the introduction of the LAR mechanism and samplers within the DSP feedback network became decisive, as a means to stabilise and vary the Larsen tones, producing variations and novelty from the basic sound material. Consequently, the technical choices in this work no longer serve primarily aesthetic ends but assume a systemic functionality. Rather than specifying sonic outcomes, the work defines interaction rules, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Genealogy of *Audible Ecosystemics*.

Feature extraction techniques, instead of being used descriptively, operate performatively: dynamic parameters modulate how system components respond to one another and to the environment. The compositional act thus moves from crafting sounds to configuring the conditions from which sound can emerge autonomously.

2. From closed to open-source

For each work in the *Audible Ecosystemics* series, detailed documentation is available from the author¹, including formal scores outlining how to replicate the systems through block diagrams (how to write the code), as well as performance procedures (how to perform the piece and reconstruct the electroacoustic chain), allowing performers to either use a patch provided by the composer or to create their own version of the pieces. The information necessary for interpreting the piece is formally complete; however, several attempts to reconstruct the works outside their original platform have proven to be technically and conceptually challenging.

The *Audible Ecosystemics* cycle was originally realised in Symbolic Sound’s Kyma, a proprietary visual programming language for sound design that runs on dedicated DSP hardware. Because Kyma is closed-source, as recently highlighted by Marco Matteo Markidis (Markidis 2024) in his reimplementation of *Audible Ecosystemics n.3* in Pure Data, even minor differences in the implementation of DSP objects can invalidate the entire compositional process. In our reimplementation, we use Faust: Functional Audio Stream (Orlarey 2004), an open-source functional programming language for efficient real-time DSP that allows for sample-wise operations. Our implementation has no external dependencies, making the software completely transparent and self-contained.

In Kyma, any audio-rate signal can be used as a control source; when this occurs, its update rate is internally reduced to a standard control-rate frequency. Faust, on the other hand, does not make a distinction between audio-rate and control signals: it operates at a true sample-rate resolution, processing individual samples rather than per control block.

Consequently, even when block-diagram structures are formally identical, their behaviour may differ significantly due to differences in software implementation and hardware processing.

In the next sections, we examine the reconstruction of the main modules of the piece and the design choices adopted, with the goal of preserving the behaviour of the original system and work rather than pursuing literal code equivalence.

3. Basic cycle section with LAR mechanism

At the centre of *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* lies the main feedback loop with the LAR mechanism: Audio Feedback with Self-Regulated Gain (Di Scipio 2022). The sound from the speakers feeds back into the microphones, closing the chain onto itself². We then introduce a

¹ Except for *Audible Ecosystemics n.1*, where the formalization of specific processes that are strongly machine-dependent, such as the separation of the impulse within the resonant space for the processing of the tail of the reflections, has over time proven difficult to translate into machine-independent notations and is still a work in progress.

² If the amplification is sufficient, the sound from the speakers feeds back into the microphones, creating a “reinjection” circuit and producing the Larsen effect: a self-sustaining feedback resonance generated by a positive feedback loop.

real-time processing computer to estimate the input amplitude, allowing us to implement a basic amplitude-following technique. The extracted control signal is then applied to complement the feedback gain of the input signal. This specific control signal design introduces negative feedback into the feedback loop: any increase in sound level decreases the feedback gain, while any decrease in sound level increases it. This mutual balance forms what we call a self-limiting, or self-regulating, feedback loop.

Figure 2: Generation of the control signal in the LAR mechanism.

Figure 3: Direct feedback loop auto-regulated by the control signal.

In these excerpts from the score of *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, we can observe the application of the LAR mechanism in the basic cycle. In Figure 2, the input signal passes through two filters to limit the input band (to remove undesired lower and higher frequencies). The integrator then transforms the signal into a control signal, sample by sample, and the delay line with feedback slows the curve produced by the integrator. The low-pass filters at the end of the chain smooth the control signal, reducing abrupt transitions between values. In the second excerpt, as shown in Figure 3, the same input signal is first limited in the audio band and then complemented by the generated control signal illustrated in Figure 2.

3.1. The Integrator

A crucial component for implementing the LAR mechanism (and other control signals) is the integrator, as shown in Figure 2, which is responsible for extracting a continuous estimate of the input signal amplitude. Di Scipio’s score describes it as an object that returns the average absolute value over a specific time frame, suggesting several possible implementations, such as a finite moving average (FIR) filter, an exponential moving average (IIR), or a windowed RMS. However, this proved problematic in early reimplementations, since the exact nature of the operation has direct consequences on the dynamics of the feedback loops, and even small deviations can compromise the systemic functions of the piece. To clarify the behaviour of the Integrator, we measured Kyma’s AmplitudeFollower object via impulse response analysis, finding that the resulting curves exhibit a classic exponential decay, characteristic of a single-

pole filter. We then examined the Kyma Reference Manual (Symbolic Sound Corporation N.D.), which defines the AmplitudeFollower object as an object that follows the amplitude of the input by taking an average of the absolute values of individual input samples.

No mention is made of time windows or block-based operations, clearly suggesting a per-sample exponential averaging. Taken together, the measurements and the documentation confirm that the Integrator corresponds to a one-pole low-pass filter applied to the absolute value of the input signal.

It is important to note that, in both Di Scipio's Kyma implementation and our Faust version, higher-order filters are realised as a series of cascaded first-order sections. Unlike Butterworth filters, and unless analytical cutoff correction is applied, cascades of first-order filters at a given cutoff will shift the frequency response. For the higher-order lowpass, particularly, we will have a much slower filter response, which can affect the system dynamics significantly.

3.2. The Delay with feedback

Another component used to implement the LAR (and other control signals) is the delay with feedback. The Kyma Reference Manual specifies that the delay module offsets the input signal by placing the delay line in the feedforward path. However, the manual does not indicate what occurs when the internal signal of the delay line exceeds the range $[-1, +1]$. Through tests, by sending constant values to the input with positive feedback and subsequently introducing negative feedback after the threshold was exceeded, we observed that the delay feedback loop is hard-clipped to this range. When the accumulated value in the loop returns to an operational range below the clipping limit, the signal decays immediately, demonstrating that Kyma never computed values outside this range in the first place. We also observed that other Kyma modules, such as certain filter designs, may exhibit similar behaviour, although our investigation was limited to the objects explicitly used in the score.

4. Resampling section

Another crucial aspect of the *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* implementation concerns the behaviour of Kyma's sample players, implemented via the Sample object. In Kyma, the MemoryWriter object cyclically writes the incoming signal into a DSP's wavetable memory for a duration defined by a time parameter in seconds. Kyma's samplers implement classical resampling-based transposition, where playback speed determines both pitch and duration according to an inverse proportional relationship, and where pitch updates continuously during playback (rather than fixed-pitch chunks). We measured that when the effective portion of the buffer being read becomes shorter than a certain threshold, Kyma's samplers gradually attenuate the amplitude of the sample until reaching silence. We reproduced this phenomenon through a lookahead-based envelope mechanism: when each sample read completes its cycle, it generates a trigger that launches an envelope on the amplitude of a delayed copy of the signal. As the trigger period becomes comparable to or shorter than the envelope duration, the fade-in/fade-out envelopes

overlap and interrupt one another, producing a progressive attenuation that leads to silence for very short fragments. Without this attenuation behaviour, very short chunks would cause the sampler to behave like an oscillator, continuously repeating the few unwindowed samples within the feedback loop, producing pitched tones unrelated to the piece and DC offset problems.

Figure 4: Highlighted Resample section; other details on the score page have been omitted for clarity.

In this excerpt shown in Figure 4, we can see that the signal coming from microphones 1 and 2, after the LAR mechanism, is written into a buffer. From this buffer, there are five main sample reads, each reading the stored signal with different parameters determined by various control signals generated in other parts of the score. These samplers introduce variations within the main loop, transposing the Larsen tones and creating textures and harmonic overlaps according to the mapping of the generated control signals.

5. Granular processing

The last layer in the audio processing chain of the piece is granular sampling. The granular engine reads from the same buffer used in the Resample section. The score specifies an object that reads sample sequences from successive buffer memory segments and shapes each segment with a pseudo-Gaussian envelope. The implementation should allow time-stretching (i.e., slower memory-pointer increments at the grain level), as well as controls for grain density and slight random deviations (“jitter”) in grain parameters. No frequency shifting is required. The

specific implementation is left to the interpreter’s choice, as long as it provides control over grain density and the resulting “sonic dust” satisfies the required criteria.

For the overlapping grains, we produced N phasor-driven grains with staggered initial phases in N different parallel instances, so that each grain starts halfway through the previous one, with the overlap controlled by the density parameter. To update grain parameters at the beginning of each grain, we use a sample-and-hold function via phase-locking: triggered by the moment when each phasor (range $[0, 1]$) that reads the buffer wraps around (when a phasor wraps from 1 back to 0). At each trigger event, the external control values are locked (sample-and-held) for the duration of the grain.

Figure 5: Granular Sampling section in the score.

In this last excerpt from the score shown in Figure 5, we can see the granular sampler. Several parameters change dynamically during the process: `mem.pointer` defines the reading position of the granulator; `jitter` introduces slight random variations in this position at each grain; `grain duration` controls the length of each grain, while `duration jitter` adds small deviations to this length at every trigger; finally, `density` controls the number of overlapping grains active at a given moment.

6. Conclusions

This work presents a specific case study in the context of sustainability in live electroacoustic music (Bernardini and Vidolin 2005), particularly regarding the transmission of machine-independent live electronic music. Since the composer is not only the author of a composition but also of a performative practice, the realisation of *Audible Ecosystemics n.2* required not only a technical translation of implementation details, but also a careful study to ensure a suitable technical baseline for preserving the piece’s systemic functions. This approach allowed us to maintain the composer’s original intentions even when necessary approximations were made.

The use of Faust has made the system transparent, enabling the analysis of details that were previously opaque in a proprietary environment, and making works that were previously inaccessible available to the community through public and transparent documentation in order

to ensure their preservation. Similar issues may arise when implementing works by other composers, where careful study of hardware, scores, block diagrams, and performance practices is required. In this context, the overarching goal of this work is to illustrate a case study that demonstrates how a composition of this kind and its performative practice can be preserved and reconstructed through available documentation.

7. References

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